

A General-Purpose CMOS Vision Sensor with In-Pixel 5-bit Convolutional Layer Computation

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Abstract—Hardware accelerators for deep convolutional neural networks (CNN) commonly reduce the bit-depth of weights and input feature maps to decrease both circuit complexity and power consumption. Nevertheless, even when the input image is codified with less number of bits, still an analog-to-digital conversion is required, being this one of the most energy-hungry parts of an image sensor datapath. In this work, a smart pixel with processing capabilities to process the first layer of a CNN is presented. In this architecture, information captured from the sensor is fed directly into the CNN accelerator, reducing the power consumption and input error, which is only limited by the analog processing circuitry non-idealities. Programmability includes stride configuration and kernel size selection between 3×3 , 5×5 and 7×7 . This paper provides data based on nominal simulations in standard 180 nm CMOS technology.

Index Terms—image sensor, CNN, hardware accelerator, focal plane processing

I. INTRODUCTION

Artificial intelligence (AI) solutions for computer vision typically require a great amount of computation power, which normally translates into systems with power consumption of the order of tenths or hundreds of watts occupying a large area [1]. In many applications these two handicaps are not an issue, as the required machines can be connected directly to the power lines and they do not need to be moved often. However, in the field of Internet of Things (IoT) low power consumption is a must, as systems are usually battery-powered, and optimized low-power techniques must be applied. By bringing the computation close to the sensors, in what is called edge-computing, a large amount of power consumption is saved in data transmission, with the additional benefit of less bandwidth requirements.

Recently, a large effort has been put into low-power hardware accelerators for convolutional neural networks (CNNs), as they are one of the fundamental steps in deep learning algorithms for video and image processing [2], [3]. The key mathematical operation of these layers is multiplication and accumulation (MAC), where each pixel of the input feature map is multiplied by a certain weight and summed up with the corresponding values of their neighbors. In this line, previous work of the authors relies on the design of a CNN hardware accelerator for up to 16 input and output feature maps for 3×3 3D convolutions with a ReLu as activation function [4]. The key idea behind said implementation is the time-current

Fig. 1: Programming and neighbor connectivity architecture of the proposed system.

multiplication, that works by integrating currents proportional to the kernel's weights for a time proportional to each input feature map value. Thus, with all the pixels in a kernel patch integrating their output current on the same summing capacitor, its final voltage will be the result of the MAC.

One of the drawbacks of this idea is that the input value must be fed into the system from the outside each time a new frame needs to be processed. To reduce the amount of data transmitted, some solutions found in the literature preprocess the captured image on the same die with column-wise or pixel-wise processing units [5], providing subsequent circuitry with some data already processed, and with that, data bandwidth and power consumption are reduced. Nevertheless, these hardware architectures are commonly constrained to kernel sizes of 3×3 . The approach we introduce here goes one step forward, as we introduce a proof-of-concept CMOS vision architecture simulated in standard 180 nm CMOS technology with in-pixel processing and kernel and stride programmability without any computing time overhead.

This paper is organized as follows. Section II describes the system architecture and the pixel design. Section III shows electrical simulations for a pixel and an array of 16×16 pixels, proving the system feasibility. Finally, Section IV concludes and summarizes the paper.

Fig. 2: Simplified schematic of the proposed pixel architecture.

II. PROPOSED VISION SENSOR ARCHITECTURE

The main goal of this work is to implement a vision sensor with in-pixel processing capabilities for general-purpose convolutional neural networks. For that, each pixel can be considered as a processing unit with local logic that allows the system to be programmed in different configurations, forming kernel patches of different sizes, namely 3×3 , 5×5 or 7×7 .

The system architecture is shown in Fig. 1. Its core is an array of identical pixels which contain the circuitry required for image capturing and processing. Also, each pixel's multiplier output is connected to its four neighbors through switches handled by local logic, as it will be explained in the next section. This logic is implemented with a custom designed 3-bit SRAM, which shares the data line coming from the INPUT DATA block and with its I/O interface managed by the wordlines ($WL_{0,1,2}$) coming from the WL selector block.

A. Core Circuitry

Fig. 2 shows the proposed pixel architecture, where the input image is captured with a conventional 3T-APS with a source follower (SF) as output buffer. In this work, a global shutter operation is achieved by sampling the output of the source follower into the capacitor C_H . The stored value will be used as the negative input of the comparator shown in the schematic. Therefore, by applying a negative slope voltage ramp to the positive terminal, a light-to-PWM signal converter is implemented. Furthermore, as the captured value is stored, the corresponding PWM value might be generated as many times as required by the following circuitry.

The last element in the pixel is the multiplier, the circuit responsible for the multiplication and accumulation operation required by the CNNs. This processing block, with its schematic shown in Fig. 3, relies on the current-time product. That is, the voltage on the C_{SUM} capacitor when it is charged/discharged at a certain constant current I_{out} takes the form:

$$V_{OUT}(T_{READ}, I_{out}) = V_{pch} + \frac{I_{out}}{C_{SUM}} \times T_{READ} \quad (1)$$

where V_{pch} is the initial precharged voltage and T_{READ} the pulse width of the PWM signal. Thus, setting the current proportional to a certain weight W and being T_{READ} proportional

Fig. 3: Schematic of the proposed analog multiplier.

to the light intensity, we can perform the inner product of the first layer in a CNN.

To set the desired current level at each pixel multiplier, before each multiplication the V_{BIAS} corresponding to a particular weight W is sampled on the capacitor C_{MEM} setting the voltage V_{MEM} . This voltage determines the desired current level flowing through the current source transistors, $M_{biasP,N}$, whereas the switches M_{sw1-4} connect or disconnect the biasing voltage to the upper or lower branch if the sign is positive '0' or negative '1', respectively. Then, the switches M_{Ptread} , M_{Ntread} connect the supply voltage and ground node for the time T_{READ} , increasing or decreasing the amount of charge accumulated on the capacitor C_{SUM} and thus providing an output voltage, OUT , directly proportional to the $I_{out} \cdot T_{READ}$ product.

The rationale behind the current-time multiplier architecture of Fig. 3 is to reduce as much as possible the parasitic capacitances between the transistors that implement the positive and negative current sources and, even more importantly, to make this parasitic capacitance constant and non dependent on the input signals (both T_{READ} and W), thus reducing the non-linear errors. Unlike our previous work [4], in this new version only one multiplier with configurable bias instead of one multiplier per bit is used, reducing the impact of parasitic capacitances of those current sources connected to C_{SUM} that are not providing any current, as well as decreasing the number of required devices and silicon area. In addition, current switching is implemented by the biasing voltage towards the gate of $M_{biasP,N}$ and a switch transistor between ground/ V_{dd} and the PMOS/NMOS current source, connecting directly the current sources to the summing capacitor.

B. Periphery Blocks

The digital to analog conversion to produce kernel weights is located in the periphery of the pixel array. Kernel weights

Fig. 4: Simulation results of the proposed pixel for the computation of four multiplications with a single light exposure.

Fig. 5: 5-bit weight DAC for current sources biasing.

are codified with 5 bits (one for sign and four for magnitude), and are converted into the biasing voltage, $V_{BIAS}(W)$, of each pixel current source. The block that generates said biasing voltage is shown in Fig. 5, and it works by mirroring the input biasing current, which corresponds to the most significant bit current, I_{MSB} , and generating four copies divided by factors 1, 2, 4 and 8, which are enabled/disabled with each input weight bit. Then, these currents are summed up determining the biasing voltage for the PMOS current sources, $V_{BIASPMOS}$, by the diode-connected transistor M_P . Then, the summed current $I_{BIAS}(W)$ is mirrored again, setting the biasing voltage of the NMOS current sources, $V_{BIASN MOS}$, by the diode-connected transistor M_N . Finally, a multiplexer chooses between $V_{BIASPMOS}$ and $V_{BIASN MOS}$ according to the sign bit of the weight, either '0' or '1'.

To distribute the biasing voltages previously described, and some other digital configuration signals, two important blocks are required in the periphery. One of them is the column selector, which controls the $WL_{0,1,2}$ signals of each column. These are activated synchronized with the data coming from the INPUT DATA block, which generates the programming

Fig. 6: Timing diagram for a 3×3 kernel with stride = 1.

bits that are written into each pixel's SRAM block (see Fig. 1). Both digital control blocks feature a programmability level that allows the user to select the kernel size and the desired stride. This configuration is performed before each of the processing subcycles required to apply the convolution kernel over all the image, following the timing diagram of Fig. 6.

III. RESULTS

The simulated behavior of the proposed pixel can be seen in Fig. 4. The pixel has two well-separated operation stages: the exposure and the computation. The exposure stage corresponds to a conventional 3T-APS operation, where a photodiode is reset to a certain voltage value, and then is left to evolve as function of the incident light intensity during the exposure time. At the end of the exposure time, the 3T-APS output voltage, V_{oAPS} , is sampled into the capacitor C_H by activating the *Sample* signal, determining the voltage V_H . In the computation operation stage, the sampled voltage V_H is compared to a ramp voltage V_{RAMP} as many times as required, obtaining the pulse T_{READ} with a width dependent on V_H . Just before each ramp cycle, signal WL_2 is activated, setting the biasing voltage $V_{bias}(W)$ and the multiplier signal $SIGN$ according to the particular weight, as well as the summing capacitor voltage, OUT , is reset to a user programmable V_{pch} voltage, which in this particular example was set to $V_{pch} = 900$ mV. Four different weights, $W_{(1)} = 00011$, $W_{(2)} = 01111$, $W_{(3)} = 10011$ and $W_{(3)} = 11111$ were used. As can be seen in (1), (2), (3) and (4) in Fig. 4, the output voltage of the pixel is increased or decreased depending on the sign and the value of the weights. The result of each operation must be

Fig. 7: Input image

Fig. 8: Output images using 3×3 filters: calculated and result of simulating a 16×16 array of proposed pixels.

sampled just before the next WL_2 high level (green dots on the detailed compute plot).

To validate the correct operation at system level, an array of 16×16 pixels has been simulated taking as input the image shown in Fig. 7. The first simulation executed was a Gaussian blurring over the image with a kernel of size 3×3 and stride 1. Even when the architecture is designed as general purpose for any given filter, this decision was made for an easy visual validation of the whole system. Results of this convolution for the ideal case and from the electrical simulation are shown in Fig. 8a and Fig. 8b, respectively. It can be seen how close the simulation computed image is with respect to the ideal. To further validate the array behaviour, an edge detector was also applied to the input image, achieving the expected output that can be seen in Fig. 8c and Fig. 8d.

As explained before, through the proper configuration of the pixel logic and periphery blocks, it is possible to implement any given kernel size and stride. To prove this point, an electrical simulation of another Gaussian blurring was executed over the input image but, differently from previous simulation, in this case a kernel size of 5×5 with stride 2 was applied. For such a small input image the result does not provide

(a) Blurring calculated. (b) Blurring simulated.

Fig. 9: Output images using 5×5 filters and stride 2: calculated and result of simulating an array of 16×16 proposed pixels.

much visual information. However, by comparing the ideal result (Fig. 9a) with the simulation result (Fig. 9b), the system correct operation can be assured.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This work introduces the first steps towards the design of an IC with a novel architecture of a CMOS vision sensor with a programmable architecture for CNNs first layer computation. Each pixel is provided with the logic required for kernel size and stride configuration, a 3T-APS, and the circuitry to perform the MAC operation in the mixed domain. Pixel area estimation leads to a pixel size of $20 \times 20 \mu\text{m}^2$ containing a photodiode of $4 \times 4 \mu\text{m}^2$, reaching a processing time of $9 \mu\text{s}$ for a 3×3 kernel or a 5×5 with stride 2. Furthermore, this time is independent of the pixel array size, as the processing is performed pixel-wise, and as the captured image is sampled this processing could be executed while the next frame is being captured. Future work includes power consumption estimation and optimization and the design of the digital control blocks that make the system fully-programmable.

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